

Research on High Precision Modeling Technology for Critical Safety Analysis of Non-uniform Two-Phase Fuel System

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ABSTRACT

This paper tackles the critical challenge of assessing nuclear criticality safety in non-uniform, dynamic two-phase fuel systems prevalent in the nuclear fuel cycle. Traditional methods, which rely on steady-state assumptions, are often inadequate for processes such as plutonium oxalate precipitation and MOX fuel production, where material distributions are highly random and anisotropic. To address this gap, we developed a high-precision modeling methodology centered on the NFPRDP (Nuclear Fuel Particles Random Distribution Program).

The NFPRDP program employs the Direct Simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) method to simulate stochastic particle behavior. It integrates multi-physics principles to model particle motion under forces including gravity, buoyancy, and fluid drag, as well as collision interactions. The program is designed for key industrial conditions such as dissolution/precipitation and stirring/centrifugation. The computational workflow involves module selection, parameter input, core calculation with decoupled motion-collision algorithms, and comprehensive data output.

Verification studies demonstrate the robustness of the program. Regularity checks show the maximum effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) for dynamic random distributions is significantly lower than for idealized uniform arrays (e.g., 0.3349 vs. 0.5658), highlighting the conservatism of traditional models. Stability testing across 120 samples per condition yielded k_{eff} standard deviations ≤ 0.0047 , confirming output with high consistency.

In conclusion, the NFPRDP program enables a best-estimate, high-precision approach to criticality analysis. By providing realistic depictions of in-process fuel distributions, it allows for more accurate risk assessment and identification of greater inherent safety margins, significantly enhancing the safety basis for nuclear fuel facilities.

Keywords: Critical Safety Analysis, non-uniform system, fuel distribution

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear criticality safety is a fundamental aspect throughout the entire nuclear fuel cycle, encompassing the production, processing, storage, transportation, and reprocessing of nuclear materials^[1]. In recent years, the global nuclear sector—including scientific research, production tasks, nuclear energy, and the nuclear fuel cycle—has entered a new phase of development. The construction of new facilities, application of new processes, upgrading of existing ones, and development of new technologies all pose fresh challenges to nuclear criticality safety practices and personnel. In the production and reprocessing of new types of nuclear materials, systems involving multiphase uranium-plutonium mixtures and many-body interactions are often encountered. Therefore, research on criticality safety for systems containing highly enriched uranium and plutonium is essential to provide more robust safety guarantees for fuel production facilities^[2].

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During nuclear material production in the fuel cycle and spent fuel reprocessing, processes such as fuel particle dissolution, diffusion, and precipitation are commonly involved. The distribution and movement of these particulate fuels are often highly random. Traditional criticality parameter calculation software is generally limited to steady-state systems, meaning it operates under known fuel particle distribution conditions within a solution system. It cannot determine the specific state of particulate fuel within the solution, which introduces significant uncertainty into traditional calculation methods.

Hence, in many processes such as plutonium oxalate precipitation, MOX fuel production, and feed dissolution, the dynamic changes of materials in solution exhibit strong anisotropy, with mixing processes showing distinct granular distribution characteristics. To address the random distribution of materials, it is necessary to fully account for heterogeneity effects and establish large-sample statistical analyses. In response to these characteristics, research should focus on developing multiphysics-coupled particle flow models using numerical methods, creating computational programs to simulate dynamic material changes and granular distributions, and establishing dynamic change models. Subsequently, validated criticality safety analysis methods can be applied to solve for k_{eff} , forming a criticality safety analysis and evaluation approach suitable for anisotropic and dynamic conditions. The computational stability and reliability of these methods should be studied to determine their feasibility for best-estimate criticality safety analysis. Comparisons with traditional conservative model analysis methods will help quantify safety margins and address the current lack of reasonable modeling approaches for randomly distributed particulate materials.

2. THEORETICAL METHODS

2.1. Principle of particle motion

Particles undergo accelerated motion under the combined action of gravity, buoyancy, impact force, and fluid drag force. According to Newton's second law:

$$m_i \frac{dv_i}{dt} = \sum F_i = \sum_{j \neq i} F_{ij} + F_{g,j} + F_{d,i} + F_{p,i}, \quad (1)$$

where m_i is the particle mass; t is time; F is the force vector; v is the particle velocity vector. Particle diameter determines parameters such as volume, mass, and the area subject to drag force $F_{d,i}$, thereby playing a decisive role in particle motion characteristics. Gravity $F_{g,i}$ and buoyancy $F_{p,i}$ are also determined by the particle's size and density. Generally, the gravity and buoyancy acting on a particle can be expressed by classical mechanics theory, and the drag force can be calculated from the relative velocity (relative to the liquid):

$$F_{g,j} = m_i g. \quad (2)$$

$$F_{d,i} = -\frac{u_r}{|u_r|} C_D A \frac{\rho_l u_r^2}{2}. \quad (3)$$

$$F_{p,i} = -\rho_l g V_i. \quad (4)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration vector; ρ_l is the liquid density; V_i is the particle volume; u_r is the relative velocity between the particle and the liquid; A is the projected area of the particle; Specifically, the elastic collision force experienced by a particle is provided by interacting particles. Due to the extremely short collision time, the effect of elastic collision on particle velocity can be neglected, mainly manifesting as a change in the particle's direction of motion.

By discretizing Equation (1) using finite difference and solving the nonlinear equation numerically with the Newton-Raphson method, the particle velocity information at each time node for a specific time step can be calculated. Then, the particle position information is calculated by applying the adaptive Simpson integration algorithm to Equation (5).

$$\frac{dS_i}{dt} = v_i. \quad (5)$$

where S_i is the position vector of the particle.

2.2. Collision

2.2.1. Particle Interaction

Particle groups experience mutual collisions during motion and settling stages. Since the particle number density within the vessel is relatively low, scenarios involving three or more particles colliding simultaneously can be excluded.

Since particle deformation is neglected, collisions are treated as rigid-body interactions, where particles change direction before and after collision. To facilitate calculation in the program, a Cartesian coordinate system is used for the particle's local coordinates, and the direction of motion is represented as a unit vector in the Cartesian coordinate system. The key point here is to derive the new direction vector in the Cartesian coordinate system after collision using the pre-collision motion direction vector and the reflection angle relative to this direction after collision. Vector projection is used for derivation in this research project, and the coordinate relationship is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Relationship of Particle Motion Direction in Cartesian Coordinate System Before and After Collision

2.2.2. Particle-Wall Interaction

When particles contact the container wall, they rebound. Assuming this collision process is an elastic specular collision, the incident and reflection paths of the particle lie on opposite sides of the normal direction at the collision point, and the scalar velocity of the particle remains equal before and after collision. For particles with relatively high velocity, multiple specular rebounds may occur after collision. Based on the scenario shown in Figure 2, this program solves the particle-wall collision path. The velocity vectors before and after collision obey:

$$(v_{i,1} + v_{i,2}) \cdot n = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$|v_{i,1}| = |v_{i,2}|. \quad (7)$$

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram of Particle-Wall Interaction

2.3. The DSMC (direct simulation Monte Carlo) Method

The DSMC (Direct Simulation Monte Carlo) method developed by Bird is a method that directly starts from the physical model of particle motion^[3]. The essence of this method is to decouple the particle motion and collision processes within a time step Δt , where Δt is much smaller than the local mean particle collision time^[4]. The flow field is divided into grids of linear scale. Spatial grids are used to select collision pairs from and to sum particle quantities to obtain macroscopic quantities of the particle group motion. The number of collisions N_t occurring in a grid within time Δt is:

$$N_t = \frac{nN}{2} \overline{S(c_r)} \Delta t . \quad (8)$$

where n is the number density in the grid; N is the number of particles in the grid; $\overline{S(c_r)}$ represents the average collision probability.

The probability P_D that two particles forming a collision pair collide within time Δt is equal to the ratio of the volume swept by the collision cross-section S at relative speed c_r to the grid volume V_c :

$$P_D = \frac{F_N S \Delta t}{V_c} . \quad (9)$$

where F_N is the number of real particles represented by a simulated particle.

The mean free path λ_i of a particle is expressed as:

$$\lambda_i = \frac{|v_i|}{f_i} . \quad (20)$$

where f_i is the particle collision frequency.

3. PROGRAM DESIGN

The calculation process is as follows:

- (1) Module Selection: Includes precipitation-precipitation condition, dissolution-precipitation condition, stirring-precipitation condition, and centrifugation-precipitation condition.
- (2) Parameter Input: Users input simulation parameters through a graphical interface. These parameters mainly include geometric, MONK file (for template generation), particle, and calculation parameters. The program then generates corresponding template files.
- (3) Run Core Calculation Program: Based on the selected condition, initializes the position and size distribution information of the droplet group, completes flow field initialization and grid division; according to the time step, progressively solves the particle motion equation, nests the calculation of particle collision and other interaction processes based on the DSMC method, and completes the update of particle size and spatial position.
- (4) Simulation Data Processing: Mainly outputs simulation calculation data. Calculation data are divided into data file output and visual output. Calculation data are output in text format designed for further data analysis and processing. The total particle mass and calculation progress are displayed in real-time during the calculation.

The programming block diagram of the DSMC method is shown in Figure 3.

c. Stirring precipitation condition
d. Centrifugal precipitation condition

Figure 4 Particle position distribution under different working conditions at various times

4. VERIFICATION OF THE PROGRAM CALCULATIONS

4.1. Regularity Verification

Based on the typical structure of post-processing equipment, the criticality safety analysis calculation program for fuel random distribution modeling, the NFPRDP V1.0 was used to carry out program regularity verification work. The liquid level height in the container is constant, the precipitated particles are plutonium oxalate ($\text{Pu}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$), and air exists above the solution. Calculation parameters such as container structure and fuel particle size, as shown in Table 1, are input into the program to construct the random distribution model. Consider the placement of 300 plutonium oxalate fuel pellets, each with a diameter of 1 cm, into a stainless steel cylindrical container with a height of 0.5 m and an inner diameter of 0.595 m. The wall thickness of the cylindrical container is 0.005 m, and the liquid level inside the container is 0.2 m. Using the criticality safety analysis calculation program for fuel random distribution modeling, input the above parameters into the calculation program to simulate the precise material distribution models of the fuel pellets under gravity-driven dissolution, centrifugation, stirring, and precipitation conditions.

Table 1 Calculation parameters for the regularity verification system

Container height (m)	0.5
Outer diameter of container (m)	0.6
Vessel wall thickness (m)	0.005
Height of liquid level (m)	0.2
Density of particles (g/cm^3)	11.469
Particle diameter (m)	0.01
Number of particles	300

For the dissolution condition input parameters, based on the parameters in Table 1, the dissolution rate was set to 20 wt%/T. For the centrifugation and stirring condition input parameters, based on the parameters in Table 1, the rotation speed was set to 300 rpm. For the precipitation condition input parameters, based on the parameters in Table 1, the precipitation rate was set to 20 wt%/T. The random distribution models for different conditions and time points were each calculated five times. The results obtained are shown in the figure below.

Figure 5. Critical safety state changes under four conditions

Using the same parameter settings from the table above, considering fuel particles evenly dispersed in the solution in an equidistant array, the effective multiplication factor obtained at this time is 0.3601. Considering the optimal moderation array distribution of particles, the effective multiplication factor is 0.5658. The maximum effective multiplication factors for the dissolution, stirring, centrifugation, and precipitation conditions are 0.3349, 0.1528, 0.1610, and 0.2152, respectively. Therefore, constructing high-precision models that closely resemble real scenarios for different fuel processing conditions not only allows exploration of criticality state changes during material evolution but also plays a crucial role in identifying enhanced criticality safety margins.

4.2. Stability Verification

According to the input conditions in Section 4.1, the fuel random distribution model was generated multiple times. Random distribution models for different conditions at fixed time points were calculated separately. These models were used as input files for the criticality safety analysis calculation program MONK to perform criticality safety calculations, obtaining the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} for each condition. The variation pattern of the critical safety state in the calculation results was statistically analyzed to conduct stability verification work.

By inputting parameters to generate randomly distributed particles, particle position information parameters were obtained, and files capable of performing criticality safety calculations were generated. For 120 randomly selected output files, their k_{eff} values were calculated using MONK, and the variation pattern across these files was statistically analyzed, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 6 Distribution of multi-sample calculation results under four conditions

Standard deviation was used to characterize the stability of the NFPRDP program. The smaller the statistical standard deviation of k_{eff} for the model files, the better the stability of the models generated by the program. The standard deviation formula is:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{(x_1 - \bar{x})^2 + (x_2 - \bar{x})^2 + \dots + (x_n - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}} \quad (31)$$

The results show that for the dissolution condition, the standard deviation statistical result of k_{eff} for the selected 120 model files is $s_1=0.0036$; for the stirring condition, the standard deviation statistical result for the selected 120 model files is $s_2=0.0046$; for the centrifugation condition, the standard deviation statistical result for the selected 120 model files is $s_3=0.0047$; for the precipitation condition, the standard deviation statistical result for the selected 120 model files is $s_4=0.0044$. The standard deviation of all calculation results from the random distribution model criticality safety analysis program is $\leq 0.5\%$.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented research on high-precision modeling and simulation technology for solid-liquid two-phase non-uniform systems, which are prevalent in nuclear fuel processing and production. Based on the DSMC method, the NFPRDP program was developed. It enables the modeling of fuel particle dynamics under dissolution, stirring, centrifugation, and precipitation conditions. It can accurately evaluate the critical safety state of complex two-phase systems and further explore the critical safety margin of fuel processing production process systems.

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